

NOTES

Trinuclear Adducts of Some Cu(II) Complexes

M. S. PATIL and J. R. SHAH*

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University,
Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120

Manuscript received 3 July 1981, revised 17 February 1982,
accepted 13 August 1982

In our attempt to prepare adducts of metal complexes of some substituted 2-hydroxy-acetophenone-thiosemicarbazones¹ we have obtained trinuclear adducts of Cu(II) complexes with some nitrogen donors. We report here the synthesis and characterization of these complexes.

Experimental

All the chelating ligands used in the present study were prepared following the literature methods. All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. In the preparation of the adduct complexes, the required amount ligand and 2 g of base was dissolved in minimum amount of ethanol. This solution was added dropwise and with constant stirring to an ethanolic solution of copper chloride in such way that the required metal : ligand ratio is maintained. The reaction mixture thus obtained was kept for 20 min in hot water bath. The brown product was filtered, washed well with ethanol and dried at 45°. All physicochemical studies were made as described earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1. All complexes correspond to $Cu_3L_3L'_3Cl_3$ compositions, where $H_2L=2$ -hydroxy-acetophenone-thiosemicarbazone (HAT), 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-acetophenone-thiosemicarbazone (3MeHAT), 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-acetophenone-thiosemicarbazone (4MeHAT) or 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenone-thiosemicarbazone (5MeHAT) and $L'=o$ -toluidine, m -toluidine or p -toluidine. Very low specific conductivities in ethanol indicate their non-ionic behaviour.

The visible reflectance spectrum of each copper(II) complex shows very broad absorption in the region 14000-18000 cm^{-1} . The observed spectra eliminate the possibility of tetrahedral or pseudo-tetrahedral structure for the complexes². The broad band of each complex shows structures (Table 1) at ~ 15000 cm^{-1} and ~ 18000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^3B_{1g} \leftarrow {}^3B_{1g}$ and ${}^3E_g \leftarrow {}^3B_{1g}$ transitions, respectively for a square planar stereochemistry^{3,4}.

The observed magnetic moments of the complexes, per gram-atom of Cu(II) are given in Table 1. These values are very close to the μ_{max} (2.24 B.M.) which could be attained by the ferromagnetic interaction and in absence of orbital contribution⁵. However, the observed values are very far from the μ_{min} (1.00 B.M.) which could be obtained in the presence of very strong antiferromagnetic interaction. Therefore, it may be stated

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTIVITY, ELECTRONIC AND MAGNETIC DATA OF ADDUCTS OF Cu(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	Analysis %, Found (Calcd.)						$\lambda_{sp} \times 10^4$ cm^{-1}	Electronic spectral data cm^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.
	Metal	C	H	N	S	Cl			
$Cu_3(HAT)_3(o\text{-tolu})_3Cl_3$	22.98 (21.42)	44.35 (43.15)	4.75 (4.26)	13.90 (12.59)	8.45 (7.19)	8.45 (7.90)	14.9	15500, 18180	2.12
$Cu_3(3MeHAT)_3(o\text{-tolu})_3Cl_3$	22.09 (20.77)	45.65 (44.46)	4.65 (4.57)	12.85 (12.21)	7.24 (6.96)	8.16 (7.72)	2.8	15680, 17850	2.01
$Cu_3(4MeHAT)_3(o\text{-tolu})_3Cl_3$	22.89 (20.77)	45.75 (44.46)	4.24 (4.57)	12.95 (12.21)	7.70 (6.96)	7.25 (7.72)	1.2	15380, 18520	2.06
$Cu_3(5MeHAT)_3(o\text{-tolu})_3Cl_3$	22.29 (20.77)	45.25 (44.46)	4.20 (4.57)	13.58 (12.21)	7.33 (6.96)	6.75 (7.72)	10.9	14450, 18180	1.95
$Cu_3(HAT)_3(m\text{-tolu})_3Cl_3$	22.86 (21.42)	44.42 (43.15)	4.68 (4.26)	13.45 (12.59)	8.21 (7.19)	7.29 (7.90)	5.5	15500, 18180	2.14
$Cu_3(3MeHAT)_3(m\text{-tolu})_3Cl_3$	22.12 (20.77)	45.42 (44.46)	4.68 (4.57)	13.43 (12.21)	8.21 (6.96)	7.50 (7.72)	5.9	15290, 17850	2.13
$Cu_3(4MeHAT)_3(m\text{-tolu})_3Cl_3$	22.35 (20.77)	45.76 (44.46)	4.52 (4.57)	12.75 (12.21)	8.32 (6.96)	7.24 (7.72)	1.6	15380, 18660	2.05
$Cu_3(5MeHAT)_3(m\text{-tolu})_3Cl_3$	22.30 (20.77)	45.86 (44.46)	4.46 (4.57)	12.84 (12.21)	8.32 (6.96)	7.58 (7.72)	5.0	15500, 18520	2.01
$Cu_3(HAT)_3(p\text{-tolu})_3Cl_3$	22.92 (21.42)	44.51 (43.15)	4.68 (4.26)	13.55 (12.59)	8.18 (7.19)	7.12 (7.90)	17.2	15630, 18180	2.06
$Cu_3(3MeHAT)_3(p\text{-tolu})_3Cl_3$	22.23 (20.77)	45.92 (44.46)	4.76 (4.57)	13.12 (12.21)	7.09 (6.96)	7.36 (7.72)	4.5	15160, 18180	2.14
$Cu_3(4MeHAT)_3(p\text{-tolu})_3Cl_3$	22.12 (20.77)	45.68 (44.46)	4.35 (4.26)	12.95 (12.59)	8.29 (6.96)	7.73 (7.72)	10.6	16180, 18180	2.16
$Cu_3(5MeHAT)_3(p\text{-tolu})_3Cl_3$	22.38 (20.77)	45.76 (44.26)	4.12 (4.26)	13.65 (12.59)	7.32 (6.96)	7.80 (7.72)	1.9	15380, 18520	3.08

very safely that the observed higher than the spin-only values of the magnetic moments of the complexes might be due to the ferromagnetic interaction⁶.

All ligands show bands in the ν_{OH} regions. The absence of ν_{OH} in all the complexes indicate the removal of phenolic proton on coordination. The low energy shifting of ν_{C-S} in all the complexes suggests the participation of sulphur in coordination. ν_{C-N} (1570 cm^{-1}) remains unaltered on complexation⁶. This suggests that the nitrogen of the azomethine is not involved in the coordination. The high energy shifting of ν_{C-O} suggests the presence of oxygen bridging in the complexes⁷. The observed low energy shifting of ligand band at $\sim 1490\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and high energy shifting of band at $\sim 1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate the decreased bond order of C=S and increased bond order of C-N. The presence of an additional band at $\sim 960\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes may be due to ν_{N-N} ⁸. This suggests the N-N bond elongation and C=N bond formation^{9,10}.

On the basis of the above physicochemical studies, the following general structure may be given for the complexes.

where B = *o*-, *m*-, *p*-toluidine.

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to Prof. S. R. Patel, Head, Chemistry Department, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar, Gujarat, for facilities. One of the authors (M.S.P.) is thankful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi for a Teacher Fellowship.

References

1. M. S. PATIL and J. R. SHAH, *Proc. Indian Academy of Sciences*, 1980, **89**, 387.
2. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, London, 1968.
3. L. SACCONI and M. J. CIAMPOLINI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1864, 276.
4. J. BJERRUM, C. J. BALLHAUSEN and C. K. JORGENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, **8**, 1275.
5. S. J. GRUBER, C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1805.
6. M. NARDELLI, G. E. GASPARI, G. G. BATTISTINI and A. MUSATTI, *Chem. Comm.*, 1965, 187.
7. T. TOKIL, Y. MUTO, M. KATO and H. JONASSEN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 3377.
8. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, B. T. GOWDA and A. S. MURTHY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14**, 985.
9. R. A. HAINES and K. K. W. SUN, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1968, **46**, 3241.
10. L. CAVALCA, M. NARDELLI and G. FAVA, *Acta Cryst.*, 1962, **15**, 1189.

Studies on Some Hydrazones, Semicarbazones, Thiosemicarbazones and Oximes as Ligands.

Part—IV : Some Divalent Metal Complexes

of Benzalacetone-Semicarbazone and Dibenzalacetone-Semicarbazone

R. C. MISHRA and B. K. MOHAPATRA*

Department of Chemistry, B. J. B. College,
Bhubaneswar-751 014

and

D. PANDA

Department of Chemistry, S. C. S. College, Puri

Manuscript received 8 September 1981, revised 6 August 1982,
accepted 12 November 1982

IN the programme of studies on Schiff's base complexes, complexation behaviour of bi-, tri- and tetradentate ligands have been reported earlier¹⁻⁵. It was thought worthwhile to have a comparative study of the complexing abilities of hydrazones, semicarbazones, thiosemicarbazones and oximes towards the transition metal ions. As a part of this programme, complexes of benzil phenyl hydrazone, 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone and oxime have been reported⁶⁻⁸. This communication presents some complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn and Cd salts with benzalacetone and dibenzalacetone semicarbazone as ligands prepared with a view to study the effect of substituents on the complexing ability.

Experimental

Ligands were prepared by a known conventional method⁹. Ethanolic solutions of different metal salts were reacted with the ligand in 1 : 2 proportion and the solution refluxed for 30 min to 1 hr. Solutions were concentrated in a rotary vacuum evaporator and kept standing in a refrigerator when crystalline compounds separated out. In some cases addition of petroleum ether was necessary for the isolation of the complexes. These were filtered under suction, washed with absolute ethanol and ether and dried *in vacuo*. Metal, halogen, thiocyanate and nitrogen were estimated as reported⁶ earlier. Conductance was measured in $10^{-3}M$ acetone solution of complexes using Toshniwal conductance bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens by Gouy method. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-671 spectrophotometer. Visible electronic spectra were recorded in $10^{-3}M$ chloroform solution of the compounds using Hilgerwatt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. Relevant analytical data are presented in Table I.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes belong to the general composition MLX_2 or ML'_2X_2 and ML_2X_2 , where L is

* Author for correspondence.